

Pneumoretroperitoneum, pneumomediastinum, and subcutaneous emphysema following endoscopic polypectomy: A rare adverse event

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Abstract

Intestinal perforation is a rare complication of diagnostic or therapeutic colonoscopy, with polypectomy increasing the risk of perforation. We report a case of pneumoretroperitoneum, pneumomediastinum, and subcutaneous emphysema without signs of peritonitis, acute abdomen, or systemic involvement, following an endoscopic rectal polypectomy. The condition was successfully managed with conservative treatment. Manifestations such as pneumothorax, pneumomediastinum, pneumoperitoneum, pneumoretroperitoneum, and subcutaneous emphysema as complications of colonoscopy are extremely rare. Cases with minimal perforative complications, without peritonitis, acute abdomen, or systemic involvement, are even rarer.

Take-home message: Few cases of minimal perforative complications from colonoscopy, such as retroperitoneal or intraperitoneal air, and mediastinal or subcutaneous emphysema, are reported in the literature. While early surgical intervention is the gold standard for patients with peritoneal irritation, stable patients without peritonitis may be managed with close clinical observation without surgery.

Keywords: Colonoscopy adverse event; colon perforation; endoscopic polypectomy; pneumomediastinum; pneumoretroperitoneum; subcutaneous emphysema.

INTRODUCTION

Intestinal perforation can be a complication of diagnostic or therapeutic colonoscopy, with large-scale studies (> 50,000 colonoscopies) reporting an incidence ranging from 0.005% to 0.085% [1]. Colon perforation usually presents with pneumoperitoneum; however, in rare cases, perforation of the colon, particularly involving the distal rectum, can lead to the dispersion of air into the retroperitoneal space, resulting in pneumoretroperitoneum. Pneumoretroperitoneum can further progress to pneumomediastinum, pneumothorax, and subcutaneous emphysema [2,3]. We report a case of pneumoretroperitoneum, pneumomediastinum, and subcutaneous emphysema without signs of peritonitis, acute abdomen,

or systemic involvement following an endoscopic rectal polypectomy.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 67-year-old woman with a history of previous rectal polypectomies presented to the Emergency Department approximately two hours after undergoing a rectosigmoidoscopy, reporting facial swelling without any other symptoms. During the endoscopic examination, a recurrent sessile rectal lesion (located 7 cm from the anal margin) was observed and removed using diathermy. On physical examination, subcutaneous emphysema was present in the supraclavicular, submandibular, and left parotid regions. The patient was eupneic, asymptomatic for pain, afebrile, and with normal vital signs. The abdomen was soft, non-tender, and without signs of peritoneal involvement. Chest and abdominal X-rays revealed the presence of subcutaneous emphysema with air in the mediastinal, intra-abdominal, and retroperitoneal regions (Figures 1a and 1b). A conservative, non-surgical observational approach was decided upon, consisting of strict fasting, intravenous fluids, and antibiotics (cefoxitin and netilmicin). The patient made a complete recovery and was discharged after 8 days.

Figure 1a. Abdominal X-ray: Subdiaphragmatic, Intra-, and Retroperitoneal Air. **Figure 1b.** Chest X-ray: Subcutaneous Emphysema and Pneumomediastinum.

Figure 1a

Figure 1b

DISCUSSION

Colon perforation is a well-known adverse event associated with colonoscopy. While it occurs very rarely, it is a feared complication with high morbidity and significant mortality [1]. The incidence of intestinal perforation during diagnostic colonoscopy is $< 1:500$ for all types of examinations and $< 1:1000$ in screening cases [4]. Since 2000, many large-scale studies have been conducted on perforations occurring during colonoscopy [1]. Pox et al. [5] reported the results of 2,821,392 colonoscopies performed over 6 years in Germany. To date, this cohort represents the largest database of colonoscopies worldwide. The overall perforation rate in that cohort was 0.016% (439 patients), including 279 patients who underwent polypectomy (0.46/1,000) and 160 patients without polypectomy (0.12/1,000).

Polypectomy also affects the incidence of perforation; the complication rate during screening colonoscopy varies significantly depending on whether or not polypectomy is performed. Therefore, the most significant risk factor for adverse events is polypectomy. According to six large-scale studies, the perforation rate for polypectomy ranged from 0.037% to 0.091%, compared to 0.005% to 0.077% for colonoscopy without polypectomy [5-10]. During polypectomy, perforation can occur due to involvement of the deep layers of the colon wall or excessive thermal injury.

Post-polypectomy syndrome (PPS) is defined as the progression of abdominal pain, leukocytosis, fever, and localized peritonitis [11]. PPS occurs after colonoscopic polypectomy with electrocoagulation. The incidence of PPS varies from 0.003% to 0.1% [12]. In general, PPS should be managed conservatively with medical therapy (intravenous fluids and broad-spectrum antibiotics), as the prognosis is favorable in most cases. However, in rare instances, surgical treatment may be necessary if there is an evident perforation with diffuse peritoneal signs.

Manifestations such as pneumothorax, pneumomediastinum, pneumoperitoneum, pneumoretroperitoneum, and subcutaneous emphysema as complications of colonoscopy are extremely rare [13,14]. There are few reports in the literature of minimal perforative complications (without signs of peritonitis or acute abdomen) with retroperitoneal pneumoperitoneum, intraperitoneal pneumoperitoneum, mediastinal or subcutaneous emphysema secondary to colonoscopy; in eight cases, this complication was secondary to rectosigmoidoscopy [15-22].

The mechanisms responsible for perforation during colonoscopy include electrocoagulation injuries during polypectomy, direct mechanical action of the endoscope, and barotrauma from excessive air insufflation [23]. Our case could be an example of perforation resulting from electrocoagulation injury. The anatomical pathway through which air from the extraperitoneal site reaches the chest and leads to pneumomediastinum and pneumothorax has been described by various authors [24, 25]. The soft tissue compartments of the neck, chest, and abdomen contain four regions defined as subcutaneous, prevertebral, visceral, and previsceral spaces.

Air leakage in any retroperitoneal area, such as from the colon or retroperitoneal rectum, can potentially reach these communicating regions by simply traveling along fascial/perivascular planes, resulting in pneumomediastinum, pneumopericardium, and subcutaneous emphysema of the chest and neck. A pneumothorax can occur when pneumomediastinum decompresses through the mediastinal pleura into the pleural cavity. Alternatively, free intraperitoneal air may enter the pleural cavity through small diaphragmatic fenestrations [26].

Perforations are more common in patients with multiple comorbidities, the elderly, and females [8,9,27-30]. The incidence of perforation decreases with the experience of the endoscopist [31], although experience alone is not sufficient to prevent this complication [32]. Early surgical intervention is considered the gold standard approach in the presence of signs of peritoneal irritation [33, 34]. Observation without surgical intervention should be limited to stable patients without signs of peritonitis. In such cases, the patient must be hospitalized, maintained on fasting, provided with intravenous fluid support, and administered prophylactic antibiotics [35].

CONCLUSION

Intestinal perforations as a complication of colonoscopy are rare events considering the high number of endoscopic examinations performed annually. Even more rarely (as in the case described), such events may be asymptomatic or paucisymptomatic, possibly due to good pre-examination bowel preparation, which does not lead to a picture of peritoneal inflammation. The described case is self-limiting with a good and rapid course; therefore, a conservative therapeutic approach combined with close clinical observation is recommended.

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